

O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA O'RIN-JOY, VAQT, SABAB, EGALIKNI BILDIRUVCHI PREDLOGLAR – KELISHIKLAR

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi kelishiklar, ya'ni predloqlarning ma'no farqlanishlari, grammatik shakllanishi qiyosan o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Kelishiklar, predloqlar, bosh kelishik, qaratqich kelishigi, tushum kelishigi, jo'nalish kelishigi, o'rin-payt kelishigi, chiqish kelishigi, joy predloqlari (proposition of place), vaqt predloqlari (proposition of time)

Ingliz va o'zbek tillari turli til oilalariga mansub. Bu esa til o'rganuvchilariga fonetik, leksik va grammatik qiyinchiliklarga sabab bo'lishi mumkin. Ingliz tili grammatikasini o'zlashtirishdagi qiyinchiliklardan biri **predloqlardir**. O'zbek tiliga predloqlar **kelishik qo'shimchalari** bilan tarjima qilinadi. Ingliz tilida esa 2 ta kelishik qo'shimchasi (case of nouns) mavjud: bosh va qaratqich. *Bosh kelishik (the common case)* ning qo'shimchasi yo'q. Shuning uchun, odatda, gapda ega vazifasini bajaradi. M., The student read a novel.

Qaratqich kelishigi (the possessive case) otga 's (apostrofli s) shaklini qo'shish orqali yasaladi va gapda qaratqichli birikmani hosil qiladi. M., the universite's library, the boy's ball.

Xuddi o'zbek tilidagi singari, agar qaratqichli birikmalarda otning boshqa aniqlovchi bo'lsa, qaratqich kelishigidagi ot o'sha aniqlovchilardan keyin keladi. M., the boy's new friend (bolaning yangi do'sti)

Bundan tashqari, qaratqich kelishigi ma'nosida egalikni *of predlogi* ham ifodalaydi. M., the day of holiday, the library of university.

Ko'pincha ko'plikdagi otlar uchun qaratqich, egalik ma'nosida of predlogidan foydalanamiz. M., the trees of garden, the workers of street.

O'zbek tili grammatikasida agar gapda ikkita qaratqich kelishigi ketma-ket kelib qolsa, ulardan birinchisi belgisiz qo'llaniladi. Ingliz tilida esa ulardan birinchisi apostrofli s bilan, ikkinchisi of predlogi bilan ifodalanadi. M., the father of my sister's friend (singlimning o'rtog'ining otasi)

Yuqoridagi misollardan ko'rinib turibdiki, o'zbek va ingliz tillarida moslashuvli birikmalar tuzilish jihatdan farqlanadi. Ya'ni o'zbek tilida egalik qo'shimchasini olgan hokim bo'lak qaratqich kelishigidagi tobe bo'lakdan keyin keladi (kitobning varag'i). Ingliz tilida esa aksincha, hokim qism tobe qismdan oldin keladi (the page of book). Ammo qaratqich apostrofli s yoki apostrofning o'zi

(ko'plikdagi otdan so'ng qo'shilsa) bilan ifodalanganda, oldin tobe bo'lak, so'ng hokim bo'lak keladi (the book's page).

Ma'lumki, o'zbek tilida bosh va qaratqich kelishiklaridan boshqa yana 4ta: tushum, jo'nalish, o'rin-payt, chiqish kelishiklari mavjud. Bu kelishiklarni ingliz tiliga tarjima qilishda ma'nosiga to'g'ri keluvchi so'zlar va predloqlardan foydalanamiz. Jumladan, o'zbek tilidagi o'rin-payt kelishigi, ingliz tilida in, on, at predloqlari bilan ifodalanishi mumkin. Masalan:

in — in January, in 2015, in a week;

on — on Monday, on January 15, on birthday;

at — at the weekend, at 10 o'clock.

O'rin payt kelishigining qo'shimchasi, o'rin joyini bildirganda ham ingliz tilida yuqoridagi predloqlardan foydalanamiz. Masalan:

in — in Uzbekistan, in Madrid, in our week;

on — on the sofa, on the table;

at — at the station, at school.

Ingliz tilida joy, vaqt va harakat predloqlari mavjud va ularni tarjima qilishda barcha kelishiklardan foydalanamiz. Masalan, quyidagi o'rin predloqlarining tarjimasiga e'tibor beramiz.

O'rin predloqlari (proposition of place):

Above - tepada, tepasida

Across - nargi tomonida

Against - qarshisida

Along - bo'ylab

Among - orasida

Alongsids - yonida

Around - atrofida

At - da, yonida

Away from - dan uzoqda, olisda

Before - oldin

Behind - orqasida

Below - quyida

Beneath - tagida

Beside - yonida

By - yonda

Down - pastga

From - dan

In - ichida, -da

In front of - oldida
Inside - ichida
In the middle of - ning o'rtasida
Into - ga, ichiga
Near - yaqinida
Next to - dan keyingi, -ning yonidagi
Off - dan
On - da, ustida
Opposite - ro'parasida
Out - tashqariga
Out of - dan tashqariga
Outside - tashqarida
Over - ustidan
Through- orqali
To - ga
Under - tagida
Up – yuqoriga

Ko'rib turganimizdek, ushbu predloglar –da o'rin-payt kelishigi, -dan chiqish kelishigi, -ga jo'nalish kelishigi, -ning qaratqich kelishiklari yordamida tarjima qilindi.

Vaqt predloglari (proposition of time):

Vaqtни ifodalash uchun ingliz tilida eng ko'p **in, at, on** predloglari qo'llanadi.

In predlogi oy, fasl nomlaridan, kun qismlari, yil, asr raqamlaridan oldin keladi.

M., in April, in summer, in the evening, in 2012, in XI.

At predlogi soatlar bilan, *present, moment, now, noon, night, midnight, weekend* so'zlari bilan ishlatiladi. M., at 8 oc'lock, at the moment, at midnight, at the weekend.

On predlogi hafta kunlari (on Thursday), aniq sanalar (on November 2), hafta kunlarining ma'lum qismi (on Monday morning), muhim va alohida belgili kunlar (on a cold day) oldidan keladi.

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